

Some Remarks on Fuzzy Neutrosophic σ -Baire Spaces and Other Fuzzy Neutrosophic Spaces

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Abstract. In this paper we define some results and examples on fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire spaces and other fuzzy neutrosophic spaces. Also we discuss several characterizations of other fuzzy neutrosophic spaces namely fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, fuzzy neutrosophic submaximal space, fuzzy neutrosophic almost resolvable space and fuzzy neutrosophic almost irresolvable space.

Keywords: Fuzzy Neutrosophic dense set; Fuzzy Neutrosophic G_δ -set; Fuzzy Neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense Set; Fuzzy Neutrosophic Baire space; Fuzzy Neutrosophic σ -Baire; Fuzzy Neutrosophic P -space; Fuzzy Neutrosophic Submaximal Space; Fuzzy Neutrosophic almost resolvable Space and Fuzzy Neutrosophic Almost Irresolvable Space.

1. Introduction

The fuzzy idea was invaded all branches of science as far back as the presentation of fuzzy sets by L. A. Zadeh [19]. The important concept of fuzzy topological space was offered by C.L. Chang [3]. The idea of fuzzy σ - Baire Spaces was introduced by G. Thangaraj and E. Poongothai [12]. The concept of neutrosophic sets was defined with membership, non-membership and indeterminacy degrees. In 2017, Veereswari [18] introduced fuzzy neutrosophic topological spaces. The idea of fuzzy neutrosophic Baire space was introduced by E. Poongothai and E. Padmavathi [7].

In this paper we investigate several characterizations of fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire spaces and also study the interrelations between fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire spaces, fuzzy neutrosophic Baire space, fuzzy neutrosophic almost resolvable spaces, fuzzy neutrosophic P -space and fuzzy neutrosophic submaximal spaces.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [2] A fuzzy neutrosophic set A on the universe of discourse X is defined as $A = \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle$, $x \in X$ where $T, I, F : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x), F_A(x) \leq 3$, with the condition $0 \leq T_{A^*}(x) + I_{A^*}(x), F_{A^*}(x) \leq 2$

Definition 2.2. [2] A fuzzy neutrosophic set A is a subset of a fuzzy neutrosophic set B (i.e.,) $A \subseteq B$ for all x if $T_A(x) \leq T_B(x)$, $I_A(x) \leq I_B(x)$, $F_A(x) \geq F_B(x)$

Definition 2.3. [2] Let X be a non-empty set, and $A = \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle$, $B = \langle x, T_B(x), I_B(x), F_B(x) \rangle$ be two fuzzy neutrosophic sets. Then $A \cup B = \langle x, \max(T_A(x), T_B(x)), \max(I_A(x), I_B(x)), \min(F_A(x), F_B(x)) \rangle$
 $A \cap B = \langle x, \min(T_A(x), T_B(x)), \min(I_A(x), I_B(x)), \max(F_A(x), F_B(x)) \rangle$

Definition 2.4. [2] The difference between two fuzzy neutrosophic sets A and B is defined as $A \setminus B(x) = \langle x, \min(T_A(x), F_B(x)), \min(I_A(x), 1 - I_B(x)), \max(F_A(x), T_B(x)) \rangle$

Definition 2.5. [2] A fuzzy neutrosophic set A over the universe X is said to be null or empty fuzzy neutrosophic set if $T_A(x) = 0$, $I_A(x) = 0$, $F_A(x) = 1$ for all $x \in X$. It is denoted by 0_N

Definition 2.6. [2] A fuzzy neutrosophic set A over the universe X is said to be absolute (universe) fuzzy neutrosophic set if $T_A(x) = 1$, $I_A(x) = 1$, $F_A(x) = 0$ for all $x \in X$. It is denoted by 1_N

Definition 2.7. [2] The complement of a fuzzy neutrosophic set A is denoted by A^C and is defined as $A^C = \langle x, T_{A^C}(x), I_{A^C}(x), F_{A^C}(x) \rangle$ where $T_{A^C}(x) = F_A(x)$, $I_{A^C}(x) = 1 - I_A(x)$, $F_{A^C}(x) = T_A(x)$. The complement of fuzzy neutrosophic set A can also be defined as $A^C = 1_N - A$.

Definition 2.8. [2] A fuzzy neutrosophic topology on a non-empty set X is a τ of fuzzy neutrosophic sets in X satisfying the following axioms.

- (i) $0_N, 1_N \in \tau$
- (ii) $A_1 \cap A_2 \in \tau$ for any $A_1, A_2 \in \tau$
- (iii) $\cup A_i \in \tau$ for any arbitrary family $\{A_i : i \in J\} \in \tau$

In this case the pair (X, τ) is called fuzzy neutrosophic top. space and any fuzzy neutrosophic set in τ is known as fuzzy neutrosophic open set in X

Definition 2.9. [1] The complement of a fuzzy neutrosophic set A in a fuzzy neutrosophic top. space (X, τ) is called fuzzy neutrosophic closed set in X .

Definition 2.10. [1] Let (X, τ) be a fuzzy neutrosophic top. space and $A = \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle$ be a fuzzy neutrosophic set in X . Then the closure and Interior of A are defined by $I.(A) = \cup\{G : G \text{ is a fuzzy neutrosophic open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$ $C.(A) = \cap\{G : G \text{ is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed set in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq G\}$

Definition 2.11. [1] Let (X, τ) be a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space over X . Then (i) $C.(A^C) = (I. A)^C$, (ii) $I.(A^C) = (cl A)^C$

Definition 2.12. [7] A fuzzy neutrosophic set A_N in a fuzzy neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set if $A_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where $\overline{A_{N_i}} \in \tau_N$ for $i \in I$

Definition 2.13. [7] A fuzzy neutrosophic set A_N in a fuzzy neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (P, τ_N) if $A_N = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where $A_{N_i} \in \tau_N$ for $i \in I$

Definition 2.14. [7] A fuzzy neutrosophic set A_N in a fuzzy neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic dense if there exist no $fnCS$ B_N in (P, τ_N) s.t $A_N \subset B_N \subset 1_X$. That is $fn(A_N)^- = 1_N$

Definition 2.15. [7] A fuzzy neutrosophic set A_N in a fuzzy neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic nowh. dense set if there exist no non zero $fnOS$ B_N in (P, τ_N) s.t $B_N \subset fn(A_N)^-$. That is $fn(((A_N)^-)^+) = 0_N$

Definition 2.16. [7] Let (P, τ_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic top. space. A fuzzy neutrosophic set A_N in (P, τ_N) is called fuzzy neutrosophic one category set if $A_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where A_{N_i} 's are fuzzy neutrosophic nowh. dense sets in (P, τ_N) . Any other fuzzy neutrosophic set in (P, τ_N) is said to be of fuzzy neutrosophic two category.

Definition 2.17. [7] A fuzzy neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called fuzzy neutrosophic one category space if the fuzzy neutrosophic set 1_X is a fuzzy neutrosophic one category set in (P, τ_N) . That is $1_X = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where A_{N_i} 's are fuzzy neutrosophic nowh. dense sets in (P, τ_N) . Otherwise (P, τ_N) will be called a fuzzy neutrosophic two category space.

Definition 2.18. [5] Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space then (X_N, T_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space if $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where λ_{N_i} 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ - nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) .

Theorem 2.19. [5] In a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) a fuzzy neutrosophic set λ_N is fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense in (X_N, T_N) if and only if $1_N - \lambda_N$ is fuzzy neutrosophic dense and fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) .

Theorem 2.20. [5] If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic dense set in (X_N, T_N) such that $\mu_N \leq (1_N - \lambda_N)$, where μ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) then μ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) .

Theorem 2.21. [7] Let (P, τ_N) be a fy. neutrosophic top. space. Then the following are equivalent.

- (1) (P, τ_N) is a fy. neutrosophic Baire space.
- (2) $f_n(A_N)^+ = 0_N$, for every fy. neutrosophic one category set A_N in (P, τ_N) .
- (3) $f_n(B_N)^+ = 1_N$, for every fy. neutrosophic re. set B_N in (P, τ_N) .

Definition 2.22. [9] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic submaximal space if for each fuzzy neutrosophic set A_N in (X, τ_N) such that $(A_N)^- = 1$ then $A_N \in \tau_N$ in (X, τ_N) . That is (X, τ_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic submaximal space if each fuzzy neutrosophic dense set in (X, τ_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic open set in (X, τ_N) .

Definition 2.23. [9] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic resolvable space if there exist a fuzzy neutrosophic dense set A_N in (X, τ_N) such that $(1 - A_N)^- = 1$. Otherwise, (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic irresolvable space.

Definition 2.24. [9] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic hyperconnected space if every non-null fuzzy neutrosophic open subset of (X, τ_N) is fuzzy neutrosophic dense in (X, τ_N) .

Definition 2.25. [9] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space if each fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X, τ_N) is fuzzy neutrosophic open set in (X, τ_N) .

Definition 2.26. [9] A fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic almost resolvable space if $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (A_{N_i}) = 1$, where (A_{N_i}) 's in (X, τ_N) are such that $(A_{N_i})^+ = 0$, otherwise, (X, τ_N) is called a fuzzy neutrosophic almost irresolvable space.

Theorem 2.27. [4] If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) , then there is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set δ_N in (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_N \leq \delta_N$

Theorem 2.28. [5] Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space. Then the following are equivalent

- (1) (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space.
- (2) $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$ for every fuzzy neutrosophic σ - first category set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) .
- (3) $\text{cl}(\mu_N) = 1_N$ for every fuzzy neutrosophic σ -residual set μ_N in (X_N, T_N)

3. On Fuzzy Neutrosophic σ -Baire Spaces

Proposition 3.1. If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N)

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) . Then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set such that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Since λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set, $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic closed sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$ implies that $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$. But we have $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) \leq \text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}))$. This implies that $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) \leq 0_N$. That is, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} \text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. Hence we have $\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$ for each i . Since (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic closed, $\text{cl}(\lambda_{N_i}) = \lambda_{N_i}$. Then $\text{intcl}(\lambda_{N_i}) = \text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$. That is $\text{intcl}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$ for each i . Hence (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Therefore $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense sets, implies that λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.2. If the fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) .

Proof. Let the fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where $1_N - \lambda_{N_i} \in T_N$. Since λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set, we have $\text{intcl}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$ in (X_N, T_N) . Now $\text{int}(\lambda_N) \leq \text{intcl}(\lambda_N)$ implies that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Hence λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ set such that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.3. If each fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) .

Proof. Let each fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Since λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) , we have $\text{intcl}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Now $\text{int}(\lambda_N) \leq \text{intcl}(\lambda_N)$, implies that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) \leq 0_N$. That is, $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Hence λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set such that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . Then by proposition 3.1, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.4. *If a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed set in a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space, by theorem 2.28, $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$, by hypothesis, λ_N is fuzzy neutrosophic closed in (X_N, T_N) . This implies that $\text{cl}(\lambda_N) = \lambda_N$. Then $\text{intcl}(\lambda_N) = \text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. That is, $\text{intcl}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$ in (X_N, T_N) . Hence (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.5. *If a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set, then (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space.*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) such that $\text{intcl}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Then $\text{int}(\lambda_N) \leq \text{intcl}(\lambda_N)$ implies that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) \leq 0_N$. Hence for a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) , we have $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Hence by theorem 2.28 is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space. \square

Proposition 3.6. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) , then there exist a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set δ_N in (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_N \leq \delta_N$.*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) . Then by proposition 3.1, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then by theorem 2.27, there is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_N \leq \delta_N$. \square

Proposition 3.7. *If $cl(\bigwedge_{i=1}^N(\lambda_{N_i})) = 1_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic dense and fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) and then $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^N(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_{N_i} 's ($i = 1$ to N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then by Theorem 2.19, $1_N - \lambda_{N_i}$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic dense and fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . Since $cl[\bigwedge_{i=1}^N(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})] = 1_N$. Now, $cl[\bigwedge_{i=1}^N(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})] = 1_N$, implies that $cl[1_N - \bigvee_{i=1}^N(\lambda_{N_i})] = 1_N$. Then we have $1_N - int[\bigvee_{i=1}^N(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})] = 1_N$. This implies that $int[\bigvee_{i=1}^N(\lambda_{N_i})] = 0_N$ \square

Proposition 3.8. *If a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space, then $cl[\bigwedge_{i=1}^N(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})] = 1_N$, where the fuzzy neutrosophic sets $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic dense and fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space. Then $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^\infty(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^N(\lambda_{N_i})) \leq int[\bigvee_{i=1}^\infty(\lambda_{N_i})]$ implies that $int(\bigvee_{i=1}^N(\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$. Then $1_N - int(\bigvee_{i=1}^N(\lambda_{N_i})) = 1_N - 0_N = 1_N$. Then we have $cl(1_N - \bigvee_{i=1}^N(\lambda_{N_i})) = 1_N$. This implies that $cl(\bigwedge_{i=1}^N(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})) = 1_N$. Since λ_{N_i} 's ($i = 1$ to N) are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) By theorem 2.19 $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic dense and fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . \square

4. Fuzzy Neutrosophic σ -First Category Sets and Fuzzy Neutrosophic P -Spaces

Proposition 4.1. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is not a fuzzy neutrosophic dense set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let us assume that the contrary. Suppose that λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) such that $cl(\lambda_N) = 1_N$. Then $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^\infty(\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Since (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets, (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -sets and $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$ ($i = 1$ to ∞). Then $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, the fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic open sets in (X_N, T_N) . Let $\mu_N = \bigwedge_{i=1}^\infty(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$. Then μ_N is a non-zero fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, μ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic open set in (X_N, T_N) and

hence $\text{int}(\mu_N) = \mu_N$. Now, $\mu_N = 1_N - \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N - \lambda_N$. Then we have $\text{int}(\mu_N) = \text{int}(1_N - \lambda_N) = 1_N - \text{cl}(\lambda_N) = 1_N - 1_N = 0_N$. This implies that a contradiction. Hence, in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category sets are not fuzzy neutrosophic dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 4.2. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space then $\text{int}(1_N - \lambda_N) \neq 0_N$*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) . Then by proposition 4.1, λ_N is not a fuzzy neutrosophic dense set. That is, $\text{cl}(\lambda_N) \neq 1_N$. Then, $1_N - \text{cl}(\lambda_N) \neq 0_N$. This implies that $\text{int}(1_N - \lambda_N) \neq 0_N$. \square

Remark-1:

In view of the above proposition 4.2, we have the following: In a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , the interior of a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -residual set is non-zero in (X_N, T_N) .

Proposition 4.3. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_{σ} -set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. If λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Since (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets, (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic F_{σ} -sets and $\text{int}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N (i = 1, 2, \dots, \infty)$. Then $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic G_{δ} -sets in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, the fuzzy neutrosophic G_{δ} -sets $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic open sets in (X_N, T_N) . Let $\mu_N = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$, then μ_N is a non-zero fuzzy neutrosophic G_{δ} -set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\mu_N = 1_N - \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})$, we have $\mu_N = 1_N - \lambda_N$ and hence $\lambda_N = 1_N - \mu_N$. Since μ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic G_{δ} -set in (X_N, T_N) , λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_{σ} -set in (X_N, T_N) . Hence in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , then the fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category sets are fuzzy neutrosophic F_{σ} -sets in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 4.4. *If (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire and fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, then each fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire and fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's

are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space, by theorem 2.28, $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space by proposition 4.3, the fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Hence λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set such that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . Hence, if (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire and fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, then each fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 4.5. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic hyperconnected and fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N)*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic hyperconnected and fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, by proposition 4.3, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set and hence $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set. Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic open in (X_N, T_N) . Again since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic hyperconnected space the fuzzy neutrosophic open set $1_N - \lambda_N$ is fuzzy neutrosophic dense in (X_N, T_N) . That is $\text{cl}(1_N - \lambda_N) = 1_N$. Then we have $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Hence λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set such that $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Therefore, in a fuzzy neutrosophic hyperconnected and fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , the fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 4.6. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic hyperconnected and fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic hyperconnected and fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) . Then by proposition 4.5, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . Then by proposition 3.1, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 4.7. *If (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire, fuzzy neutrosophic P -space and fuzzy neutrosophic hyperconnected space then (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space.*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire, fuzzy neutrosophic P -space and fuzzy neutrosophic hyperconnected space (X_N, T_N) . Then by proposition 4.6, λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire space, by theorem 2.28 $int(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Hence, for the fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) , we have $int(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Then by theorem 2.28, implies that (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space. \square

Proposition 4.8. *If each fuzzy neutrosophic open set is fuzzy neutrosophic dense in a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire and fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) , then (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space.*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in a fuzzy neutrosophic Baire and fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, by proposition 4.3, the fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Again, since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, $1_N - \lambda_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic open set in (X_N, T_N) . By hypothesis, $1_N - \lambda_N$ is fuzzy neutrosophic dense in (X_N, T_N) . That is, $cl(1_N - \lambda_N) = 1_N$. Then $1_N - int(\lambda_N) = 1_N$ and hence $int(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Hence for fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) , we have $int(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. By theorem 2.28, (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space. \square

Proposition 4.9. *If λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) then λ_N is not a fuzzy neutrosophic dense set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space (X_N, T_N) . Then by proposition 3.6, there exists a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set δ_N in (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_N \leq \delta_N$. Then $1_N - \lambda_N \geq 1_N - \delta_N$. Since δ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -set, $1_N - \delta_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space $1_N - \delta_N$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic open set in (X_N, T_N) . That is $int(1_N - \delta_N) = 1_N$. --- (1). Now, $\lambda_N \leq \delta_N$ implies that $1_N - \lambda_N \geq 1_N - \delta_N$. Then $int(1_N - \lambda_N) \geq int(1_N - \delta_N)$ and hence $int(1_N - \lambda_N) \geq 1_N - \delta_N$ from (1). Since $1_N - \delta_N \neq 0_N$, $int(1_N - \lambda_N) \neq 0_N$. Then $1_N - cl(\lambda_N) \neq 0_N$. This implies that $cl(\lambda_N) \neq 1_N$. Hence if λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense set in a fuzzy neutrosophic P -space, then $cl(\lambda_N) \neq 1_N$. Therefore λ_N is not a fuzzy neutrosophic dense set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Remark-2:

The inter-relation between fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space, fuzzy neutrosophic almost irresolvable spaces and fuzzy neutrosophic σ -second category spaces can be summarized as follows.

Proposition 4.10. *If the fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic strongly irresolvable fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space and λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) then λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space. By theorem 2.28 $\text{int}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$ in (X_N, T_N) . Then we have $1_N - \text{int}(\lambda_N) = 1_N$. This implies that $\text{cl}(1_N - \lambda_N) = 1_N$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a fuzzy neutrosophic strongly irresolvable space for the fuzzy neutrosophic dense set $(1_N - \lambda_N)$ in (X_N, T_N) , we have $\text{clint}(1_N - \lambda_N) = 1_N$. Then $1_N - \text{intcl}(\lambda_N) = 1_N$ and hence $\text{intcl}(\lambda_N) = 0_N$. Therefore λ_N is a fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 4.11. *If λ_{N_i} 's are the fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category sets in a fuzzy neutrosophic strongly irresolvable, fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space (X_N, T_N) , then $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let (λ_{N_i}) 's be the fuzzy neutrosophic σ -first category sets in a fuzzy neutrosophic strongly irresolvable, fuzzy neutrosophic σ -Baire space (X_N, T_N) . Then by proposition 4.10, (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) and hence $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$ is a fuzzy neutrosophic first category set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 4.12. *If (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to N) are fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in a fuzzy neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) and $\text{int}(\bigvee_{i=1}^N (\lambda_{N_i})) = 0_N$ then $\text{cl}[\bigwedge_{i=1}^N (\lambda_{N_i})] = 1_N$, where (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic dense and fuzzy neutrosophic G_{δ} -sets in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to N) be fuzzy neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -sets with $int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0_N$ ($i = 1$ to N). Now, $1_N - int(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$, then we have $cl(1_N - \lambda_{N_i}) = 1_N$, that is $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Since (λ_{N_i}) 's are fuzzy neutrosophic F_σ -sets, $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . Hence $(1_N - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neutrosophic dense and fuzzy neutrosophic G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now, $cl(\bigwedge_{i=1}^N (\lambda_{N_i})) = cl(1_N - [\bigvee_{i=1}^N (\lambda_{N_i})]) = 1_N - int[\bigvee_{i=1}^N (\lambda_{N_i})] = 1_N - 0_N = 1_N$ in (X_N, T_N) .

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